

METHODOLOGY OF CHECKING FALSE INFORMATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF DISINFORMATION CONFLICT

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Annotation: An analysis of the methodology of checking false information in the conditions of disinformation conflicts was carried out.

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The development of information technologies, especially the emergence of the Internet, has, firstly, increased the speed of preparation and transmission of information several times, and secondly, expanded the possibilities of receiving it to an unprecedented extent. Therefore, in this process, the correctness or incorrectness of the transmitted information is not taken into account. As a result, the purpose and content underlying the information are becoming abstract, and it is being used for various purposes and interests. False, fabricated, and fake information negatively affects the audience's consciousness, disrupting various relationships between people, existing rules, values, and traditions in society. Moreover, today, not only news published on social networks, but also in serious electronic media, especially news sites, often contain false information. This leads to consumers of news content accepting them without analyzing them and blindly believing them. Also, "in recent years, the media has become a means of exchanging ideas rather than information transmission channels. With the increasing activity of bloggers on social networks, the opinions of public leaders are gradually drawing the audience away from traditional media and Internet information resources. Materials brought to the attention of the public on social networks, blogs, forums, photo and video hosting are widely discussed among users. Modern means of communication are increasingly becoming sources of information that is disseminated unverified or based on rumors[1].

The intensification of various types of information conflicts in the world in the 21st century has increased the interest of philosophers, sociologists, and lawyers in this problem. Conflicts arise as a result of fundamental changes in human society, a clash of interests, and a mismatch of goals, and unfortunately leave many victims in their wake. If earlier there was talk of eliminating conflicts, now there is talk of managing them. To achieve success in this regard, it is necessary to systematize existing knowledge and enrich approaches, and increase citizens' awareness of conflicts. The media play a significant role in

revealing the essence of conflicts, explaining to citizens the content of social conflicts, and, if necessary, in conducting mediation activities to reconcile people and groups involved in conflict.

The availability and effectiveness of information are related to such basic consumer quality indicators as its content, adequacy, relevance, timeliness, accuracy, reliability, and stability: a) representativeness of information - is associated with its correct selection and formation in order to adequately express the nature of the object; b) meaningfulness of information - expresses its semantic (content) volume; c) sufficiency (completeness) of information - indicates that it has a minimum, but sufficient content (set of indicators) for decision-making. Incomplete, that is, insufficient, as well as excessive information in the process of making the right decision reduces the effectiveness of the user's decisions; d) relevance of information - is determined by the preservation of its value for management during the use of information and depends on the dynamics of changes in its properties, as well as the time interval that has elapsed since the appearance of this information; e) timeliness of information - indicates that it is received without delay from the agreed upon time for solving a previously defined task; f) accuracy of information - is determined by the degree of proximity of the received information to the real state of the object, process, event, etc.; g) reliability of information - is determined by the property of information to represent real existing objects with the necessary accuracy.

Speaking about the global danger of social networks, it is necessary to pay attention to the following vices that are regularly and constantly spread through them: calls by terrorist and extremist groups to oppose their homeland and people; instructions on how to use drugs and military weapons; various pornographic pictures and films; well-founded and unfounded information that serves the interests of certain groups; elements of "popular culture" that do not correspond to national values at all; online games that promote cruelty, etc.

As is known, in each social network there is an opportunity to make as many friends as you want, become a member of various groups, visit shared links, "like" distributed materials, and promote your own views. This further increases the likelihood of danger.

Any scientific discovery has more or less negative consequences, and humanity is always trying to reduce these consequences. The invention of the airplane later led to the invention of the parachute, and the creation of cars led to the emergence of traffic rules and traffic safety measures. At a time when

social networks are becoming a powerful weapon in the hands of various evil forces, it is advisable to jointly develop and popularize modern, reliable methods of protection against them.

According to journalist Rustam Jabbarov[2], the most correct way to prevent such dangers is not to restrict social networks or the Internet, as in some countries. In order to reduce the risks without giving up their useful aspects, it is necessary to use the following methods.

Virtual method. The leaders of the world's largest international and national social networks, together with mature experts and influential international organizations, should come to a unanimous conclusion on finding and deleting the accounts of organizations that threaten global security and stability, and preventing the spread of their ideas on these networks.

Legal method. In order to ensure the correct flow of information and protect against its harmful consequences, each country should create a solid legal framework for the use of the Internet, in particular social networks. It is necessary to increase administrative and criminal liability for the dissemination of such terrible ideas as aggression, racism, chauvinism, organized crime, overthrow of the constitutional order, terrorism, religious fanaticism, violence, cruelty, obscenity, elements of "popular culture", drug trafficking, illegal arms trade, human trafficking, and incitement to suicide through Internet publications and social networks, and to strengthen the existing legislative framework in this regard.

Educational method. That is, it is necessary to form the etiquette of using the Internet and social networks in every young man and woman. To do this, parents should monitor which network their child is on, what he is doing, who he is meeting, what groups he is a member of. This can probably be assessed as an infringement on the rights of young people from a Western point of view. However, from the point of view of Eastern values, it does not hurt to limit the rights and opportunities of young people in a good way. At the same time, we think that it is time to introduce training courses on the culture of using the Internet and social networks in schools and educational institutions. In this regard, textbooks and manuals should be created by experts in the field.

Propaganda method. In order for young people not to fall under the influence of various harmful trends and information attacks, it is necessary to create and popularize social networks in each country that express their political, social and cultural views and national interests. It is necessary to organize groups on Facebook, Twitter, Odnoklassniki, Vkontakte, LinkedIn and other social networks to combat the above-mentioned

global problems and to gather more young people in them. Perhaps, regulating the activities of users on social networks, introducing certain restrictions, and amending laws in this regard may seem to today's Western analysts to be contrary to democratic principles and a threat to human rights and personal integrity. However, any democratic values, the rights and freedoms of people in a certain group should not threaten the lives and security of others. In other words, it is necessary to form an internal immunity of social network users against information attacks that can be spread through these networks. We should not isolate our youth from social media, but rather turn them into intellectual representatives of society who can use it correctly and distinguish right from wrong. The forbidden fruit is sweet. However, it would not be right to completely abandon this fruit, but rather to separate the useful part for ourselves and throw away the harmful part, and teach others to do the same.

The interrelationship between human nature and the phenomenon of information has acquired special significance in the context of the beginning of the technological revolution and the rapid development of the Internet. Due to the emergence of the unlimited possibilities of the Internet, the authenticity of information has been seriously damaged. "Fake news" has spread everywhere.

Two main factors are responsible for the widespread spread of "fake news": 1) quantitative - there is a huge amount of information on the Internet that cannot be verified; 2) qualitative - technological: thanks to new technologies, the means of collecting and storing information, as well as the entities producing it and the channels for transmitting it, have increased.

If we focus on the first case, the difference between the older generation and today's youth in terms of information use is that their main sources of learning were books, documents, periodicals (newspapers, magazines, bulletins, etc.), audio media and other traditional means. In the conditions of the information society, the most important source of knowledge is the Internet. Moreover, accessing this huge "repository" does not require any effort. Today, approximately 97 percent of users consider the Internet as a source of information. For 47 percent, social media has become the main source of news. Therefore, it is the Internet, especially social networks, that is a convenient and safe place for the spread of "fake news", in our opinion. There are several reasons for this. First, the tendency to enter the information market through social networks and create content there is very easy. Second, social networks are convenient in format - it is convenient to receive news on a phone or watch it on a computer screen, but this can create difficulties for discussing the

reliability of information. Third, the number of users of social networks is growing at a very high rate. In such conditions, trust in traditional media is declining. As a result, verified sources of information are changing in favor of social networks, opening a wide path for the development of unverified, poor-quality information. Fourth, scientists have proven that social media ideologically isolate people from each other. For these reasons, the influx of a huge amount of information through the Internet and, in particular, social networks has lowered the status and position of traditional media.

Some authors give detailed explanations for the distorted form of information such as “fake news”: humor, misinformation, manipulative information, organized information, misleading content, misinterpreted information[3]. However, it is necessary to distinguish between fake news and content that carries misleading and false information. Information corruption often takes one of three forms: disinformation – disinformation: false information deliberately created with the aim of harming a person, social group or country; misinformation – incorrect information: information is false, but not created with the aim of harming a person, social group or country; malinformation – accurate information, but it is used to harm a person, social group or country[4].

All three types of information corruption are aimed at spreading false information and causing harm. It should be noted that today, societies living in a constant information environment are increasingly exposed to unreliable, distorted information. In particular, news related to political events, military operations, international events, that is, events that require important decisions, the spread of “fake” is becoming a manipulative tool. One of the greatest researchers on the impact of information on public consciousness, the Canadian philosopher Herbert Marshall McLuhan, was of the opinion that the media are “natural resources”. Therefore, in the modern world, the struggle for access to information resources has come to the fore. Understanding the nature of “fake” news based on rumors helps to clearly delimit the concepts of “information” and “disinformation”.

Disinformation is a type of information that creates a false picture of reality in the audience. The means of disinformation include complete or partial distortion of facts, concealment of information, wrong emphasis on the message in communication, etc.

In the conditions of the rapid development of information technologies and the expansion of technical capabilities, it is difficult to distinguish rumors and half-

truths, half-jokes from real ones. The reason is that now there is a technology that “allows” each user to easily copy documents, images, audio files, which is always an obstacle to reliable information. To prevent, stop and refute this, we need techniques and filters that help organize the activities of journalists at a professional level. Today, with the rapid development of new media and Internet journalism, other concepts have entered the mass media arena, which differ in the participation of the audience and the methods and means of influencing readers. Its name is mystification.

References:

1. Комиссаров М. А. “Проблема распространения недостоверной информации в СМИ и социальных медиа”// Тезисы к выступлению на 20-й Центрально-Азиатской Конференции СМИ “Будущее журналистики”. <https://www.osce.org/representative-on-freedom-of-media>
2. Jabborov R. Sources of information attacks: problems and solutions. <http://huquqburch.uz/uz/view/533>
3. The Impact of CrossCheck on Journalists & the Audience, by Smyrnaio, N., Chauvet, S., & Marty, E., November 2017
4. Claire Wardle, Hossein Derakhshan, “Information Disorder. Toward an interdisciplinary framework for research and policymaking”, Council of Europe, 2017.